

ENVIRONMENT

Methane production and emission in coastal ricefields of Texas

F. M. Fisher, Jr., R. L. Sass, and P. A. Harcombe, *Ecology and Evolutionary Biology Department, Rice University, Houston*; and F. T. Turner, *Texas Agricultural Experimental Station, Beaumont, Texas, USA*

Atmospheric methane, an important "greenhouse" gas, is increasing at a rate of about 1 % per yr. Flooded ricefields may be an important source of atmospheric methane, through anaerobic microbial processes.

Agricultural wetlands also provide a model system that can be used to examine the biological and physical processes that regulate methane production and emission.

A study in summer 1989 focused on two irrigated ricefields with different soil types: Lake Charles, a Typic Pelludert, and Beaumont Clay, an Entic Pelludert.

Jasmine 85 was drill-seeded (67 kg/ha) in rows 18 cm apart. Both fields received 39, 59, and 51 kg urea N/ha applied before planting, at flooding, and at panicle differentiation, respectively. An additional 51 kg N/ha was applied to the Beaumont Clay field when N appeared to be deficient after panicle differentiation. Thiobencarb and propanil were applied before flooding to control weeds.

The study ended at 130 d after sowing, shortly after field drainage before harvest. Grain yields were 7 t/ha on the Lake Charles soil and 6 t/ha on the Beaumont Clay soil.

Mean daily soil temperature 2 cm below the soil surface ranged from 27 to 30°C. Daily minimum temperature showed no seasonal trend, with an average of 24°C; daily maximum temperature decreased from an early season average of 31°C to an end-of-season average of 26°C. Water temperatures showed similar trends, but variations were more pronounced. Decreases in soil and water temperatures were

attributed to development of the rice crop canopy.

Water depth in the Lake Charles field was relatively stable at 6-14 cm. That in the Beaumont Clay field was more variable because damage to the levee system during tropical storm Allison early in the season resulted in water drainage. After restabilization, water depth ranged from 3 to 15 cm.

Methane emission (flux) and above- and below-ground biomass were measured at four random locations in each field. Integrated annual methane emissions ranged from 4.5 (Beaumont Clay) to 15.9 (Lake Charles) g/m² per season (determined by static flux box measurements).

Methane emission was detected from vegetated plots shortly after flooding in the Lake Charles field and was strongly related to aboveground biomass throughout the growing season (Fig. 1). Virtually no methane flux could be detected in nonvegetated plots until late in the season (Fig. 1, insert a).

No significant emission was observed in vegetated plots in the Beaumont Clay field until panicle differentiation. This delay may have been caused by the field drainage and soil aeration that resulted from levee damage (Fig. 1, day 177, insert b). The effect of field drainage and intense rainfall on exposed soils will be further examined as weather conditions permit.

Methane production, measured in laboratory-incubated soil core segments from both fields, was spatially and temporally related to live root biomass (Fig. 2). Early methane production was highest in the 0-2.5 cm soil layer associated with the dense fibrous root system near the soil surface and lowest in the 7.5-10 cm depth and between plant rows.

As the growing season progressed, methane production at lower depths and farther away from the plants increased in proportion with root density. Seasonal integrated emission in the laboratory was 42% that of the methane production measured by static flux boxes in both fields.

1. Correlation of aboveground biomass with methane emission ($r^2 = 0.92$) in the Lake Charles field and seasonal methane flux for vegetated sites (o) and nonvegetated sites (•) in the Lake Charles field (a) and the Beaumont clay field (b).

Methane production ceased when fields were drained before harvest. No methane was emitted even following prolonged incubation in the laboratory under an anaerobic nitrogen atmosphere. But when exogenous acetate was provided, methane production immediately resumed.

These results indicate that methane production and emission from flooded ricefields are dependent on plant root distribution and aboveground biomass. Soil properties and water management also affect methanogenesis. Further research relating these effects to rice cultivars and farmer practices is needed to form a basis for designing technology that would help mitigate the currently increasing levels of methane in the atmosphere. ■

2. Correlation of live root biomass with methane production from the lake Charles field (•) and the Beaumont clay field (o). Data points represent measurements taken from 4 soil depths (0-10 cm) at 3 distances from plants at 4 times during the growing season. Regression line is for the combined data set.

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Tropical crop research and biotechnology symposium planned.

The new International Society for Tropical Crop Research and Development (ISTCRAD), with headquarters in Trivandrum, Kerala, India, is organizing a symposium to coincide with its formal inauguration in September 1991.

Organizing secretary is Dr. N. K. Nayar, Department of Agricultural Botany, College of Agriculture, Kerala Agricultural University, Trivandrum 695522, India. ■

Recommendations of IRRC 1990 research discussion groups

Nearly 200 scientists from 30 countries participated in the International Rice Research Conference 27-31 August in Seoul, Korea. They discussed the research results reported in about 40 papers and posters, and identified directions for future work.

Summaries of discussion group recommendations are given below.

Direct seeded rice. A matrix was used to target problems, opportunities, and research priorities, with plant characteristics and crop management on one dimension,

and agroecological zone, inputs, and direct seeding methods on the other (see table).

Participants agreed on the need to establish a universally accessible data base: where and how is direct seeding presently practiced, where is the practice increasing, what is the yield loss or benefit, and what is the time-and-cost benefit (particularly in low-input, tropical systems with unreliable technology and low opportunity cost of labor).

Features of an ultrahigh tillering plant ideotype deserving research priority include

- Quick early growth at seedling establishment.
- Tiller population/ha = tillers/plant × plant population × tiller death.
- Nitrogen use efficiency in terms of uptake and utilization and redistribution (tied to the value of the stem as a sink/source for both N and carbohydrate and to synchronous seed filling).
- Patterns of root growth and their benefit.

Rice blast disease. Research needs include

- Integrated control — developing on-farm decision aids, agroecologi-

cal zoning, and management of panicle blast.

- Quantitative epidemiology, modeling, and forecasting — disease assessment methods, conditions affecting host susceptibility, interactions with other pests, sources of initial inoculum, crop losses, coupling blast models to crop models, fungicide dynamics, and disease forecasting.
- Host plant resistance and pathogen population virulence — gene development, genetics, screening methods, and durable resistance.

The group decided to form working groups for each area; members may undertake joint trials or other direct cooperation. The working groups and their coordinators are as follows:

Integrated control: Fernando Correa, CIAT-Rice Program, P.O. Box 6713, Cali, Colombia; and Arunee Surin, Rice Pathology Research Branch, Plant Pathology and Microbiology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok, Thailand.

Quantitative epidemiology: P. S. Teng, Plant Pathology Division, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, 1099 Manila, Philippines; and K. Manibhushanrao, Centre for